

« PrÉ » : connected polyphonic immersion

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ABSTRACT

By introducing the spatial dimension in the musical creation, a plastic parameter has been imagined already since antiquity, playing both on the structuring of spaces, and on the structuring of the effect of presence. Taking up the classifications of the sign theorist Charles Sanders Peirce, the sound as an index has always been - by its physical capacity to reach the eardrums of the spectator - the main vector of the idea of immersion. Music and sound have thus become credible forms of extended reality.

The present project thus aims to work on this notion of acoustic and immersive environment as well as on the "space" of play thus created - a form of extended reality through music, *or even music augmented by forms of objects and devices* [1] through a study of the creative processes for the composition by the PrÉ device of Jean-Luc Hervé, composer associated with the project.

The PrÉ device (for electroacoustic presence) is a multichannel diffusion system based on a singular conception of the relation of sound to place. It creates a sound environment where the audience is surrounded by multiple invisible sound sources. The system is designed to have a large number of independent voices to constitute a large polyphony. It consists of a park that can go up to several dozen sound agents, each associating a nano-computer with a mini-loudspeaker, running on batteries. The whole park is connected by a network in HOP web language controlled by a main computer, which allows to free itself from any wiring and to easily hide the sound agents in order to make the device invisible.

1. Introduction

The project has several objectives:

- Develop all-in-one modules (microcomputer, speaker, amplifier, battery), robust, easily handled and rechargeable, with an optimized acoustic quality.

- Program a simple user interface.

- Program a 3D audio environment allowing to simulate the device with a binaural listening, and thus to work the polyphonic composition upstream with the headphones.

- Adding audio (computer music) and control (IOT) functionalities

- Extend the park to a larger number of agents (64)

The goal is to make it a more generic and easy way to use system, which can be used by other composers, but also in other artistic fields (sound installation, theater, dance), pedagogical or in any field where such a system of independent, localized and proximity multi-broadcasting could be used to create a sound environment (for therapeutic purposes for example...)

- Musicology of things, performance and musical narrativity in immersive systems

In parallel, the question of the study of the creative process is posed according to a double point of view: does the production circuit influence the phases of creation? Does the technological use have an incidence on the global aesthetics of the piece [2] ?

The second question concerns musical narrativity and the study of performance. If analytical tools have been conceived to account for the construction and renewal of musical forms [3] few studies except in the field of Sound Studies [4] attempt to grasp the interaction between sound and space by mobilizing adapted tools (translation of spaces, acoustic fingerprint, spectral averaging, frequency analysis, spectral analysis).

The last question concerns a new field for musicology: the object or the device, and joins multiple realities (IoMusT, sound object, space, diffusers, transmitters) notion thought not as reduced to an artifact, but as a device at the same time real and tangible but also social and symbolic [5]. This displacement of the thought allows to inscribe the musicological study in the same chain of workflow, that is to say from the starting point of the production.

2. Methodology

The methodology concerns the *in situ* study of the development of a spatialized scholarly musical work and of technologies linked to spatialization and immersion devices.

It is doubled by an analysis of the processes of the musical composition and the setting in abyss of the various stages of the construction of the project in order to build a musicology of the objects and the devices, and an analysis of the new musical categories concerning the orchestration of the electro-acoustic musics. This project concerns a research in art and creation. Its subject is an aesthetic reflection on the relationship between music and a specific immersive electroacoustic diffusion device. This research is developed at CIRM and CTTEL and with the Conservatoire à Rayonnement Régional de Nice. The first stage of this work was realized in collaboration with Radio-France on the occasion of the creation of the work *Autre Nature* for orchestra and electronics by Jean-Luc Hervé, which was premiered at the Auditorium of the Maison de la Radio et de la Musique by the Orchestre Philharmonique de Radio-France as part of the Présences festival in February 2022.

3. Realization

3.1 Research and building speakers

Originally the dispositif *PrÉ* exists, notably through several creations by Jean-Luc Hervé. A first production took place in 2017, with CIRM and DIRCREAM, and in 2018, creation of "Retransmission" with the 2E2M ensemble, using 24 modules, including wireless modules connected in BT [Figure 1]. The project works globally on polyphony, with integrated modules, a control interface. The idea was to make the project evolve towards a more versatile and agile use.

Figure 1. First version of the module.

The issue is to create an independent, localized and proximity diffusion system. This step requires the manufacture of dedicated speakers, with the manufacture of a plastic box by 3D printing.

Figure 2. First assemblage of boxes with raspberry and speakers.

Figure 3. Frequency response of the speakers

Figure 4. 3D printing of speakers boxes.

3.2 Supervision and control of equipment

The device is a Raspberry Pi-based distributed computing system [Figure 2]. It can be installed and moved easily according to the shows. The implementation of this device poses a certain number of problems typical of both a distributed system such as supervision and synchronization, but also typical of a mobile system. The supervision is important for the follow-up of the music pieces but also at the time of the implementation of the equipment, and the

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rehearsals. The device being mobile it is necessary to be able to ensure that at each displacement it functions correctly.

The supervision consists of a Node.js[6] server that regularly queries all the equipment, each of which has a Node.js client. This client interfaces with the Raspberry Pi Operating System. The Node.js server is accessible from any terminal on the Raspberry Pi network. [Figure 5] shows the web interface of the server. It allows to check the operation of each equipment as it is installed in the theater with a cell phone for example.

In terms of control, at the time of installation, the Node.js server makes it possible to send OSC [7] commands and thus activate a test sound on a specific piece of equipment or on all the devices. This makes it possible to locate hidden equipment or to control the sound levels. The server offers system functionalities such as rebooting; shutting down any equipment remotely; transferring files between server and client. In the current version it was not necessary to implement a synchronization mechanism, but this is under consideration especially with the possibility of integrating the Skini system for the design of music pieces.

In this first version of the project the sounds are played on the Raspberry Pi using PureData [8] which receives OSC messages. In a later version, it could be possible to converge the supervision service and the playback of sounds in a single application.

Figure 5. Supervision server

4. “Autre Nature” and the concert project

Once defined, the speakers become devices [Figure 4]. They differ from the usual immersive processes because, contrary to the modes of ambisonic diffusions which use globally reconstructions of sound points by objects, the PrÉ system proposes to distribute the sound in the space. In the composition "Autre Nature" Jean-Luc Hervé composes sound instances by treating the orchestral mass from a global point of view.

Each musical texture is linked to the next in the mode of either transition or rupture. The sound envelopes are used as models to create temporal features.

Finally, by using the Open Music base to obtain specific spectral colors [Figure 3], the harmonic or rather inharmonic dimension makes it possible to manage a symbolic sound space which is very rich.

At the end of the piece, the same inharmonic instances are reproduced in the speakers.

Figure 6. Radio France Auditorium

Figure 7. Placement of the HP in the auditorium. Handwritten plan by Jean-Luc Hervé and Camille Giuglaris.

The process that begins at the end of the work appears in the tiling with the instruments. At the Festival *Présence* de Radio France in February, the placement of the speakers in the auditorium was significant. Each of the loudspeakers is equipped with a line of sound samples, it is completely autonomous and controlled by the server system [figure 5]. A max/msp patch manages the different samples for sending to the raspberry.

Figure 6. “Autre Nature”. Jean-Luc Hervé. Excerpt from the score.

When the orchestra concludes, the strings sound inharmonic accents that seem to be distributed in space. One passes from a spatialized listening to a dissemination, each loudspeaker making resound an "other nature" (like the title in French *Autre nature*) of the sound.

5. Discussion

This project, initiated by Jean-Luc Hervé, was the opportunity to make a triple experiment. First, an innovation in terms of connected loudspeaker, allowing to set up a hyper-spatialization system, a distributed space setting, controlled by a web interface (node.js/hiphop.js). Each speaker is totally autonomous and can be placed anywhere thanks to the wifi router. This gives another vision of the broadcasting space, modular and infinitely configurable, a hyperspatialization.

Finally, an innovation in terms of live performance and composition, since the fact of being able to control each of the loudspeakers in a differentiated way requires another approach to composition, and other processes of mentalization of the nature of the sound objects. An "object" both of diffusion and of symbolic conception which finds here its natural space, its "autre nature" [9].

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